

The Impact of the Brazilian General Data Protection Law (LGPD) on Public and Private Organizations

Semi-Structured Interview Protocol

Introduction:

- **Research Background:**

- This interview protocol is part of a Master's research project in Computer Science conducted at the Center for Informatics (CIn), Federal University of Pernambuco (UFPE), Brazil. The study investigates the organizational and technical impacts of the Brazilian General Data Protection Law (Lei Geral de Proteção de Dados – LGPD) on public and private organizations operating in Brazil.

- **Research Objective:**

- The objective of this study is to identify, analyze, and synthesize evidence regarding the LGPD compliance process based on the perceptions of professionals directly involved in data protection initiatives within their organizations.

- **Target Participants:**

- Professionals directly involved in LGPD compliance processes, including members of data protection committees, working groups, IT teams, legal departments, or governance structures.

- **Data Usage:**

- All data collected through interviews will be used exclusively for academic research purposes. The study focuses on understanding organizational impacts and does not aim to evaluate individual or organizational performance.

Interview Characteristics

Confidentiality:

All information collected during this interview will be treated with strict confidentiality. No personally identifiable information will be disclosed.

Estimated Duration:

Approximately 60 minutes.

Recording Procedure:

- Online interviews: conducted via Google Meet (audio and video recording for transcription purposes).
- In-person interviews (if applicable): recorded using audio or video recording tools.
- Participants must explicitly authorize the recording.

Interview Conduction:

The interview will be conducted directly by the principal researcher.

INÍCIO DA ENTREVISTA

- **Informed Consent:**
 - Participation in this study is voluntary and may be withdrawn at any time. The information collected will be treated confidentially, and no data allowing participant identification will be disclosed.
 - **Consent Question:** Do you agree to participate in this interview and authorize its recording? **(Verbal consent required)**

Record→ Date: __/__/____ Time: __:__ Location:_____

Participant Identification (for internal use only):

Name:_____

E-mail: _____

*** If the participant did not complete the survey, ask the profile questions.**

Participant Profile

1. What is your academic background?
2. What type of organization do you work for?
(Public / Private / Mixed)
3. Could you describe your role and/or position within the organization?
4. How long have you held this position?
5. What is the size of your organization?

6. In which regions of Brazil does your organization operate?
7. What is the main sector of activity of your organization?

General Perceptions of LGPD

1. What is your overall perception of the LGPD?

- a. General perspective (not specifically related to your organization or position):
- b. What is your opinion regarding compliance with the law?
- c. What is your opinion regarding the dissemination and awareness of the law?
- d. What is your opinion regarding the level of data protection established by the law?

2. How did your organization initially approach LGPD compliance?

- a. a. When did the compliance process begin?
- b. b. How was the compliance process initiated?
 - i. How was the initial planning conducted?
 - ii. What were the first activities carried out?
- c. c. In the case of selecting responsible professionals, how was this selection conducted?
 - i. Were LGPD specialists hired or engaged by the organization?
 - ii. Was external consultancy contracted?
- d. d. Were goals or deadlines established, or something similar?
- e. e. Was there any form of resistance to participation in the compliance process?
- f. f. Was any type of training related to LGPD provided?
 - i. If so, could you provide examples?
 - ii. Were they useful?
 - iii. Was there adherence/engagement from those involved?

LGPD Compliance Process

3. What is the current status of LGPD compliance in your organization?

- Has the compliance process been completed?
- If not, which phase is it currently in?
- Were the established goals achieved?
- Was the final deadline met?

- 4. How did (or how is) the LGPD compliance process occur(ing) within your organization?**
 - a. Was a committee or working group established to oversee LGPD compliance?**
 - i. Did only internal employees participate in the compliance process?**
 - ii. Were external consultants hired for the compliance process?**
 - 1. If so, did employees and consultants work together during compliance?**
 - 2. Were consultants solely responsible for the compliance process?**
 - b. What were the stages followed in the compliance process?**
 - c. Which professionals (roles and positions) were involved in the compliance process?**
 - i. How did they contribute to the compliance process?**
 - ii. Were LGPD specialists hired or engaged by the organization?**
 - iii. In your opinion, was the number and profile of professionals adequate to carry out the compliance process?**
- 5. Specifically regarding the actions taken during your organization's LGPD compliance process, which methodologies or techniques were adopted?**
 - a. Was any specific methodology or technique adopted?**
 - i. If so, which one(s)?**
 - ii. Who developed the process/methodology?**
 - iii. How was the decision made to adopt this methodology?**
 - iv. In your opinion, was the use of this methodology beneficial?**
 - b. If no formal methodology was adopted, was there any justification for this?**
 - i. Was any internal process developed?**
 - ii. Were there discussions regarding the approach to be followed?**
 - c. Which actions do you consider fundamental for the success of the compliance process?**
 - i. Please provide examples, if possible.**
- 6. Which technologies, tools, software, or systems were used by your organization in the LGPD compliance process?**
 - a. Please provide examples, if possible.**
 - b. Consent management platforms**
 - c. Data Loss Prevention (DLP) solutions**
 - d. Database firewall**
 - e. Web Application Firewalls (WAFs)**

- f. Multi-Factor Authentication (MFA)
- g. Physical security controls (restricted access to facilities and equipment to prevent unauthorized physical access, damage, or interference with personal data)
- h. Secure storage systems (mechanisms to protect records and equipment from loss, damage, theft, or compromise of personal data)
- i. Remote work security procedures (software and access control measures for remote work environments)
- j. Backup and restoration systems (routine backup procedures to restore information in case of data loss)
- k. Removable media protection controls (mechanisms to manage the use of removable media to prevent unauthorized disclosure, modification, removal, or destruction of personal data)
- l. Monitoring systems (logging user and system activities to detect and prevent data breaches)
- m. Patch and update management (keeping software up to date and applying the latest security patches)

7. How does your organization carry out the processing of personal data?

- a. How was the Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA) defined or developed within your organization?
 - 1. Controller
 - 2. Processor
 - 3. Data Protection Officer (DPO)
 - 4. Was a risk identification and assessment conducted?
 - a. Were measures implemented to mitigate identified risks?
- b. Was a Personal Data Inventory created (DPIA: record of personal data processing activities carried out by the institution, in accordance with LGPD Art. 37)?
- c. Terms of Use and Privacy Policy
- d. Web Application Security Guidelines
- e. The processing of personal data refers to any operation performed on personal data, such as collecting, accessing, classifying, storing, deleting,

distributing, printing, transmitting, or other actions necessary for service provision by controllers and processors.

f. Personal data provided to or obtained by the controller must be limited strictly to what is necessary for service provision.

g. All personal data processing must contribute directly to actions necessary for service provision by the controller or as authorized by the data subject – no more and no less.

h. Any personal data processing carried out by the processor in the provision of services must occur under the instructions and authority of the controller.

i. A natural person may act as a controller, provided that they process personal data for service provision and are remunerated for it, as is the case with independent professionals.

j. References: https://lgpd.ufba.br/sites/lgpd.ufba.br/files/cartilha_lgpd.pdf

8. How were the LGPD principles implemented within your organization?

a. Purpose Limitation

i. Specific, legitimate, and relevant purposes were clearly communicated to the data subject regarding the processing of their personal data.

b. Adequacy

i. Processing activities are compatible with the purposes previously informed to the data subject by the data processing agent (controller or processor).

c. Necessity (Data Minimization)

i. Processing and data scope are limited to the minimum necessary to fulfill the stated purpose.

d. Free Access

i. Data subjects are granted facilitated and free access to the controller regarding the form and duration of the processing of their personal data.

e. Data Quality

i. Data subjects are ensured clarity, accuracy, relevance, and up-to-date information consistent with the necessity and purpose of processing.

f. Transparency

i. Clear, precise, and easily accessible information is provided to data subjects regarding data processing activities.

g. Security

i. Data processing agents adopt appropriate technical and administrative measures to ensure data security.

h. Prevention

i. Appropriate measures are implemented to prevent damage resulting from personal data processing.

i. Non-Discrimination

i. Processing activities do not result in discriminatory, abusive, or unlawful practices.

j. Accountability and Demonstration of Compliance

i. Data subjects have the right to demand accountability for damages and evidence of the adoption of effective good practices in personal data processing.

9. How were data subject rights implemented within your organization?

a. Confirmation and Access

Confirmation of the existence of one or more processing activities carried out by the controller, and access to personal data relating to the data subject that are under the controller's custody.

b. Rectification

Correction of incomplete, inaccurate, or outdated personal data.

c. Anonymization, Blocking, or Deletion

Anonymization, blocking, or deletion of unnecessary, excessive, or non-compliant personal data.

d. Data Portability

Portability of personal data to another service provider, where applicable.

e. Deletion of Personal Data Processed Based on Consent

Deletion of personal data processed with the data subject's consent, even if previously granted.

f. Information on Data Sharing

Provision of information regarding data sharing practices with public or private entities.

g. Information on the Consequences of Refusal to Consent

Explanation of the consequences of refusing consent, including the implications of not authorizing data processing.

h. Right to Object

Objection to processing carried out without consent or in cases where the data subject identifies irregularities.

i. Withdrawal of Consent

Revocation of previously granted consent.

j. Review of Automated Decisions

Review of decisions made solely based on automated processing of personal data that affect the data subject's interests, including profiling decisions.

10. What were the main challenges faced by your organization in achieving LGPD compliance?

- a. Please provide examples, if possible.
- b. Were there any challenges related to the time available for compliance?
- c. Were there any challenges related to the professionals involved in the compliance process?
- d. Were there any challenges related to the costs associated with compliance?
- e. Were there any challenges related to the availability of specialists (e.g., DPOs) for compliance?
- f. Were there any challenges related to the organization's culture?
- g. Were there any challenges related to the internal processes adopted by the organization?
- h. Were there any challenges related to the Brazilian government, such as:
 - i. Regulatory bodies
 - ii. Supervisory authorities
 - iii. Bureaucratic requirements
- i. Were there any challenges specifically related to particular provisions of the law?
 - i. Please provide examples, if possible.

11. Based on the challenges described, can you identify possible solutions or recommended courses of action?

12. From your perspective, did LGPD compliance introduce significant changes to the functioning of the organization?

- a. Did it impact the organization's daily activities?
- b. Were new processes or practices established?
- c. Can you identify organizational changes following the implementation of the LGPD?
- d. Were the organization's strategic decision-making processes affected by the LGPD?
- e. Were there behavioral changes among professionals after the LGPD came into effect?

13. From your perspective, did LGPD compliance introduce significant changes within the IT area of the organization?

- a. Can you identify specific examples of such changes?
- b. From a security perspective, what was the main impact?

14. Would you like to add any additional information that you consider relevant to this research?

Reference

Collado, Carlos Fernández, Pilar Baptista LUCIO, and Roberto Hernandez Sampieri. "Metodologia de pesquisa." *São Paulo: McGraw* (2006).